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Ethics in Medicine

Providing humane care with dignity. An ethical challenge in aging societies.

Abstract

Does professional nursing as a person-centered service have normative foundations? Are there specific ethical questions related to nursing? How can systematic reflection on nursing ethics succeed in everyday practice? This thesis provides answers on a meta-level.

Thesis

Ethics in nursing addresses those moral and ethical dimensions that are significant in the context of the responsible nursing professional mission, interdisciplinary collaboration, and professional interaction. Ethics aims to be a guide for ethically reflected and morally justifiable nursing practice. Ethics and ethical reflection, understood as an integral part of professional nursing, are tied to the original subject area of nursing and the anthropological implications coupled with it. In the following, central ethical and moral points of orientation for nursing are

named, whereby in particular the significance of the systematized ethical reflection of values from the respective situationally inherent perspectives of those involved and affected must be accentuated. The pioneer of nursing - Florence Nightingale - made her mark with her "Nightingale's Oath". "The Nurse's Dilemma: Ethical Considerations in Nursing Practice" by Sara T. Fry influenced the nursing ethical discourse of the ICN (International Council of Nurses) already since 1977 in the Anglo-American area. Fry describes a concrete decision-making model for nursing practice and declares beneficence, justice, autonomy,

sincerity and loyalty to be the "most important principles" of nursing professional practice. As early as 1923, the ICN began work on a concept for a nursing code of ethics. This was presented - after the interruption of development work during the Second World War - in 1953 and revised several times since the first publication. The ICN Code of Ethics for Nurses as a nursing professional commitment shapes and influences the local professional ethos and in turn represents the core of the ethical identity of professional nursing. It refers to the fundamental values of human dignity and human rights, which it bases professional nursing on as normative dimensions. The professional code itself maps out cornerstones of ethical principles and standards and, going beyond ethical standardization, calls for responsible situation-related ethical consideration and reflection, oriented to the specifics of the respective nursing situation and its contexts. In the Anglo-American setting, the "Code of Ethics for Nurses" of the ANA (American Nurses Association) is guiding and determines the ethical reflection and ethical discourse there. Nursing theories - which as theoretical foundations open up a frame of reference for nursing practice and systematize and structure nursing action - also contain anthropological as well as ethical dimensions of being human and of nursing and make determinations in this regard. The caring concepts contained in individual nursing theories (e.g. Leininger and Watson) also describe a basic nursing attitude in which, among other things, nursing care plays a central role. The discourses on care ethics, the care perspective and the associated concepts (for example, the concept of mindfulness) are to be taken into account for the foundation of the moral and normative frame of reference of a nursing ethics.

Already in this focused presentation it becomes apparent that nursing has several ethical reference points: the ICN code of ethics, nursing theories with their respective value orientations such as human dignity, etc. Furthermore, current ethical reference points for nursing can be found in the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UN CRPD) as well as in the Charter of the Rights of Persons in Need of Assistance and Care. The points of reference to be named as examples (such as the ICN Code of Ethics, nursing theories, charters, UN CRPD) do not, however, solve the ethical questions and areas of conflict that exist in nursing practice with their ethical points of reference. Rather, the values named and which guide the actions of professional nursing can themselves trigger an ethical area of conflict, e.g. between the value of autonomy and care.

Ethical reflection in everyday professional nursing and the nursing relationship

In the following, exemplary ethical questions from everyday nursing work are explained in order to make the complexity of ethical questions explicit and to illustrate the importance of systematized and conscious ethical reflection for professional nursing action. Nursing as an interpersonal event in the context of interaction and encounter as well as the situational asymmetries and diversities have the potential for ethical dilemmas and moral irritations in many forms. Furthermore, the growing complexity in the nursing profession's daily routine and the accompanying increase in the areas of responsibility and demands on professional nursing contribute to the importance of ethical reflection and ethically based decision-making. The importance of nursing ethics has increased, also in view

of changed social and health policy conditions. Increased sensitivity to ethical issues is required in all fields of action of the profession: in the clinical setting, in inpatient long-term care, in home care as well as in hospice. In many cases, in addition to the genuine nursing professional perspective, a broad spectrum of contextualization (e.g., which framework conditions? which setting? which payer?) and interdisciplinarity must be considered and included. In this way, it is possible to balance the variety of potentially tangential perspective differences or to analyze them in the context of systematized ethical reflection. The respective target groups of professional care services (persons in need of care, relatives, caregivers - in each case across life phases) require specific attention as well as different starting and reference points for the assessment of individual care needs and the negotiation of appropriate care services. Care-related encounters and situations are influenced by the respective lifeworlds, life plans and life relationships of those affected and involved; the care situation is often characterized by dependence and dependency. Care-related contacts vary in intensity and duration (for example, the intensity and quality of contact may be different during a short stay in a hospital than in long-term inpatient care or in a home environment). Evidently, many factors influence care situations: Who is subjectively affected and how? Whose vulnerability needs to be protected, what needs to be taken into account? Problems in care-related contexts often arise from contradictions between the parties involved, for example, between the person being cared for and the caregiver. These contradictions in turn result from differences in personal, spiritual and/or cultural value orientations and ethical intuitions. At the same time, in every area of nursing, there is a desire on

the part of professional nurses to realize quality nursing care that is oriented toward the individual and corresponds to current nursing science findings. In other words, professional nursing wants to meet theoretical, evidence-based requirements as well as objectively ascertainable nursing needs and individual needs. For example, a certain nursing intervention - such as regular positioning - can prevent skin lesions, but is rejected by the informed person in need of care who is capable of giving consent, out of a need for situational privacy and rest. The dilemma arising from the existing discrepancy between the objective need for care (to prevent skin lesions) and the individual need (for privacy and rest) and the existing plurality of values (e.g. between care and privacy or between responsibility and self-determination) calls for systematic ethical reflection. The required decision requires - in addition to the nursing analysis and evaluation (danger of skin lesions) - positioning based on nursing ethics with regard to action or, in this example, with regard to refraining from action.

Central ethical implications

The overarching task of professional nurses in the various nursing fields of activity and under the various nursing conditions is to protect the physical and psychological integrity of all persons involved in the nursing situation. As explained at the beginning, this is particularly a matter of protecting (human) dignity, but also of respecting autonomy and rights of freedom. Furthermore, it is important for everyday professional care to reflect on the finite nature of life and the associated diverse and multifaceted ethical issues and areas of ethical conflict. This is particularly true in the specific fields of intensive care, palliative care, hospices, clinics and care for the elderly. Professional

nursing care also requires an ethically reflective, responsible and legally secure approach to living wills and other forms of advance planning, to the various forms of expressing one's will and to the often inherent discourses of autonomy and "well-being". The increasing professional care needs of people with cognitive changes-such as dementia-call for careful and systematic ethical reflection of intentional care interventions, as this group is particularly vulnerable and communication is often limited. Decision-making in people with impaired communication (as a frequent consequence of dementia) and in (elderly) people who are no longer capable of making decisions is increasingly becoming an object of professional nursing care worthy of ethical reflection in all professional fields of action. This refers not only to the "big ethical questions" (PEG yes/no with PEG referring to a special type of gastric tube: "percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy", hospitalization yes/no, curative or palliative therapy options, changes in therapy goals, euthanasia, etc.), but also to everyday nursing-related decisions in complex nursing situations, such as, for example, the handling of motor skills in the elderly. For example, dealing with emotional and physical agitation, dealing with challenging behavior (mechanical and drug restraint, sedation, administration of medications, etc.), but also protecting intimacy and privacy, participation, dealing with violent behavior and coercion, etc. The interpretations of autonomy, human dignity and, in many cases, quality of life, which vary in the decision-making situation, represent potential areas of ethical conflict. One aspect that could provoke ethical tension in this regard is the discrepancy between the formulated presumed will of a person in need of care represented by relatives and/or the legal guardian (for example, with

regard to nutrition and hydration) and the observable expressions of will (with regard to hunger and thirst) as registered by the caregivers in their round-the-clock care of the counterpart. Here, the well-intentioned care and the behavior observed and interpreted as an expression of self-determination can be the starting point for an ethical conflict, which can be concretized in the dilemma between care and autonomy or between the respective recorded will and the defined good. Care-ethical sensitivity manifests itself in everyday situations, in dealing with people in need of care in the context of the care acts themselves, in the relationship and interaction. Care-ethical sensitivity represents a fundamental ethical competence and is at the same time the prerequisite for identifying and formulating ethical conflicts as such in nursing practice. With regard to inpatient long-term care, care-ethical sensitivity means, for example, the situational preservation of and respect for autonomy, respect for the rights of freedom, or also the sensitive balancing of respect for privacy and the offer of participation. In this setting, the required ethical sensitivity is based, among other things, on the specific characteristics of a "total institution". The ethical competence of professional nurses also includes sensitivity to the genuinely ethical conflict situations in everyday nursing care, but also in the context of social and institutional developments and challenges. Ethical conflict potentials that increasingly affect nursing management result, for example, from financial pressure, the scarcity of goods in the health care system and the processes of economization, rationing and prioritization that go hand in hand with this, as well as the demand for "sustainability" in nursing decisions and actions. Current technological developments in the context of nursing

and care (such as the "therapeutic" seal Paro, which is used in the encounter with people with dementia, or the "Care-o-bot 3", a robot that is used in inpatient geriatric care to serve drinks and to encourage occupation) as well as age-appropriate assistance systems provoke specific ethical questions that, due to the technical change, affect and change the nursing-related mission as well as the nursing professional everyday life.

Nursing ethical reflection as a professional mission

Nursing ethics is not a "special" ethics. It is an ethics that relates to the specifics of ethical issues in nursing action, in nursing situations, and in the context of nursing-related encounters and interactions. It opens up and demands a specific reflection on nursing ethics. The professional assignment concretizes the task for the professional group of nurses to subject their professional actions to ethical analysis, reflection and consideration as well as to be sensitive to ethical questions in the execution of actions and in the nursing-related contexts. Understood in this way, nursing ethics does not primarily distinguish itself from other professional groups in terms of content, which does not seem desirable against the background of the premise of interdisciplinary action. Rather, the distinction is made in relation to the nursing mission itself and the original role of nurses and other medical professionals in an interdisciplinary care setting. The aim of nursing ethics is to register ethics as a genuine object of professional nursing action and to practice ethical reflection and ethically justified action responsibly. The special focus of nursing ethics is therefore not only on the individual but also on values. Both are to be demanded in the context of professional care acting as well as care-

expert relationship organization. The consequence of identifying an ethical field of tension, as in the described examples of nutrition and hydration (cf. above: PEG) or skin lesion, demands that the ethical dilemma that arises situationally be systematically reflected upon - at best in the context of an interdisciplinary ethical case discussion. The field of tension between the two conflicting values (here: autonomy and care), the ethical dilemma due to the different assessments of the will and welfare of the person in need of care, is at the same time the central object of the ethical question and the starting point for an ethical case discussion. Ethical case discussions are therefore central, structuring procedures in professional nursing care in order to arrive at ethically good, normatively correct, transparent decisions that are acceptable to all those involved. Ethical case discussions are also called for in the charters already mentioned.

Ethical aspects of standard nursing

Ethical reflection and ethical consensus are fundamental for the respective care action to be accepted as an ethically legitimate measure and to be realized as an ethically justified action (referring to the above example: by relatives, legal caregivers and professional caregivers). In the context of systematic ethical reflection, it is important to identify the guiding value orientations in each case (perspective of those involved and affected). The following questions, among others, arise here: Which values are involved and affected in the situation (autonomy/self-determination, care; is it a matter of protecting human dignity or respecting the rights of freedom? etc.)? Which value guides whom in terms of reasoning regarding existing options for action and decision-making? In this case, a different value may guide the focus of care

to the relatives/legal guardians rather than to the professional caregivers (perspective variance). Furthermore, the questions arise: Which value represents and claims truth and validity in the situation? Which orientation is guiding - more of a deontological or more of a teleological orientation? In ethical reflection, it is important to anticipate the consequences of the respective value orientation (what is the consequence of the orientation to self-determination, what are the consequences of the orientation to care, and what options for action follow from the orientation to justice?). The value conflicts are to be weighed up systematically (e.g. between the value of self-determination and care) in order to meet the demand for an ethically reflected and ethically founded decision. This complex decision can be systematized by an ethical case discussion. Nurses and all other medical professionals involved have to assume responsibility for dignified and responsible, but also ethically based care, out of the genuine nursing professional mandate. Successively, procedures and instruments of ethics counseling are also establishing themselves outside the clinical setting, such as in geriatric care facilities and hospices. In all fields of action, professional nursing and care play a decisive role in the context of quality care, and consequently the nursing ethics perspective also plays a role in ethical decision-making. This means that the nursing profession is called upon to fulfill its professional responsibility to an even greater extent and to actively participate in processes of ethical reflection and decision-making. Nurses are called upon to consistently bring the specific nursing-related ethical viewpoints, the nursing ethical expertise as well as the value conflicts involved from their perspective into the interdisciplinary ethical decision-making process (e.g. in the context of ethical case discussions and/or

ethics guideline development) in the sense of a good decision. On the one hand, this initiative should be based on the nursing profession's interest in being able to justify nursing decisions and their own nursing actions ethically, and on the other hand, it should serve to actively counteract "moral distress" or to counteract it somewhat. Because - this has been proven in the meantime - "moral distress" leads to considerable stress in the long term, up to and including burnout and professional retirement. Both established systematized forms of ethical reflection and health-promoting and relieving measures can counteract this enormous and lasting burden and contribute to moral resilience. Here, in particular, the institutions, services, the sponsors and employers have an obligation to their employees - possibly even an ethical obligation - in the sense of their duty of care for the caregivers who do extraordinary things every day for the people in need of care.

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